

THERMOMECHANICAL BEHAVIOURS OF SiC FIBERS

C. Colin, V. Falanga, K. Shimoda, L. Gélébart

CEA, Nuclear Energy Division, Nuclear Material Department,
DEN/DMN/SRMA/LC2M, CEA Saclay, 91 191 Gif-sur-Yvette Cedex, France
christian.colin@cea.fr

Keywords: SiC fibres, tensile device, high temperature, mechanical behaviour, elasticity, viscoplasticity, electrical conductivity, irradiation

Owing to progress in the manufacturing on SiC fibres (Hi-Nicalon S, Tyranno SA3), the mechanical and thermal behaviours of SiCf/SiCm composites have been sharply improved. Moreover, regarding their physical and chemical properties and their stability under irradiation, SiC/SiC composites are potential candidate for nuclear applications in advanced fission (Generation IV) and fusion reactors (ITER). These applications imply a severe environment including high temperature, fast neutrons spectrum and surrounding coolant and fuels. CEA must characterize and optimize SiC/SiC composites before their uses in reactors. In order to study this material, CEA is developing a multi-scale approach by modelling from fibers to bulk composite specimen: fibres behaviours must be well known in first. Thus, CEA developed in collaboration with LCTS a specific device for tensile tests on fibers at high temperature (up to 1800°C under secondary vacuum).

Using this device, we have already characterized the thermoelastic and thermoelectric behaviours of SiC fibers from room temperature up to 1600°C. Additional results about the viscoplastic properties at high temperatures were also obtained. Indeed, we performed tensile tests between 1200°C up to 1700°C to characterize this plastic behaviour. Some thermal annealing, up to 3 hours at 1700°C, had been also performed. Furthermore, we compare the mechanical behaviours with the thermal evolution of the electric resistivity of these SiC fibers.

Soon, MecaSiC will be coupled to JANNUS, based in CEA Saclay. JANNUS will be a unique facility of charges particles in Europe for the study of irradiation effects and ion beam modification of materials, the simulation of damage due to irradiation and in particular of combined effects. In this configuration, we will be able to study in-situ irradiation effects on fibre behaviours, as swelling or creep for example. But first, we study only irradiated fibers with Xe ions at GANIL and we show the evolution of mechanical properties during annealing treatment.